

NAVRUZ HOLIDAY VIEWS IN BUKHARA REGION

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Annotation: Navruz has been widely celebrated as a national holiday by many Eastern nations for thousands of years. There are various folk tales, songs, legends, and stories about him. The traditions of Navruz history goes back centuries, are still honored and glorified. The celebration of Navruz holiday, which embodies the traditions of glorifying the early awakening of nature and wishing blessings, also meant the consequences of hot seasons. Our ancient ancestors held a number of ceremonies on the spring equinox. Among them, Navruz has taken a special place with its enthusiasm and energy for young and old. For this, the people loved and honored him from generation to generation. For, children's participation in Navruz was considered a good sign. Others, children born in Navruz are considered lucky and have character and are considered worthy of special respect. That's why the ancient peoples connected Navruz celebrations with some mythological cults and celebrated New Year's celebrations, which were created as the day of victory of goodness over evil forces, mainly in or near shrines.

Key words: Navruz, Bukhara, Eastern nations, historical buildings, Navruz special dishes Navruz Sayli.

Navruz has been widely celebrated as a national holiday by many Eastern nations for thousands of years. There are various folk tales, songs, legends, and stories about him. The traditions of Navruz, whose history goes back centuries, are still honored and glorified. With the independence years in the historical calls of our president, it gained even more value. Navruz is a very ancient holiday. It was celebrated even before Islam, and it is not a religious holiday. Navruz was misinterpreted, and its celebration was unfairly restricted during the celebrations. The first President of our country, I.A. Karimov: Navruz is the most ancient, original national holiday for us, free from different ideologies and policies, it meets our traditions and values to renounce all malice, grudges and conflicts, and to appreciate the value of a peaceful life. The glorification of harmony and solidarity, mutual respect, and solidarity among peoples is a priceless wealth, and the Navruz holiday with its invitations is in perfect harmony with the views of our people. Because it has such a deep meaning and meaning, he explained its meaning clearly and concisely, saying that we will spend our Eastern New Year as a national holiday.

The celebration of Navruz, which embodies the traditions of glorifying the early awakening of nature and wishing blessings, also marks the defeat of the winter forces to which Ajidahaka-Bivarasp belongs, as well as the part attributed to Ahura – the consequences of the hot seasons. Meant That’s why the ancient people connected Navruz celebrations with some mythological cults and celebrated New Year’s celebrations, which were created as the day of victory of goodness over evil forces, mainly in or near shrines. In Bukhara, this ceremony was organized mainly in the shrine of Bahauddin Balogardon.

Navruz, which means a new, happy day, is celebrated on the spring equinox, that is, around March 21-22. Again, through the Sassanids, it was turned into a state holiday and celebrated in the summer, the longest day, on June 21-22. Our ancestors hold a number of ceremonies on the spring equinox. Among them, Navroz was celebrated with enthusiasm and energy, whether big or small. Hence, the people loved and honored over . The participation of children in Navuz was considered a good sign. Children who were born in Navruz are considered lucky and have character and are considered worthy of special respect. Boys born on this day are named Navruz, and girls are named Navruzoy, Bahoroy, Gulbahor, and Lola. It is considered that the new development will have a successful outcome with their participation. As the ambassador of Navruz, when children saw a tree that sprouted in early spring, they made bouquets from it, wore garlands on their heads, fell in love with the prospect of the elderly, walked from yard to yard and received their blessings. They announced the arrival of spring by singing the song “Boychechak” and sharing flowers. When the song was finished, the children were applauded while the elders were praying. They rubbed the rosary on their eyes and wished for peace and stability and blessings for the country. After that, the housewives distributed gifts and sweets to the children. The children shared those with each other .

Boychechagim boylandi, Qozon tola ayroni....

Children know this song very well. “Boy” means the god, and “chechak” means flower. The first flower that opens in the spring is considered as the flower of God among the people, and it is honored as an auspicious flower, a divine flower.

Before Navruz, seven rows of seeds of seven types of grain crops were planted. These consisted of wheat, barley, flax, millet, peas, oats, and rice. Depending on their growth, the level of productivity of the year is estimated. Water was sprinkled on the ground. With this, it is desirable to have water and livestock throughout the year. On this day, people exchanged gifts, grudges were forgotten, and wars were stopped. There are seven different dishes on the Navruz table, and these dishes begin with the sound “sin” in the Arabic script. These consisted of hazorispan (sipand), apple (seb), ink (sedona), sinjid (olive oil), vinegar, garlic, sabzi (wheat grass). In the center of the table are seven branches of trees such as willow, olive, quince, pomegranate, and mulberry.

The pink color is placed in one container and pure water in another container. Fruit tree leaves are thrown on clean water. Bread, yoghurt, milk, cheese, dyed eggs, chicken meat, dried fruits, nuts, almonds, pistachios, fish, and glass (mirror) are placed on the table. The candles lit for the Navroz table are supposed to burn until the end. Also, special dishes such as “Goja soup, Sumalak, and Halim “were prepared for the table. In addition, Navruz festivities lasted for forty days, mostly until the middle of May, and included various ceremonies. Rituals such as sumalak, boychechak, and lola sayli (the red flower of the saili) are considered to be part of Navruz and are canceled during this period. In some places, people used to tell fortunes by looking at children’s playing in the spring. It is said that if children play peacefully, friendly, and cheerfully, the year will be good, but if they quarrel and play loudly, the year will be turbulent and difficult. On Navruz days, in Bukhara, Muchal ceremonies are usually canceled for children who have turned 12 and turned 13. The Muchal ceremony is held when the child is born in the year of the animal named after the year of that name. Let’s say that this year, boys and girls who were born twelve years ago in the year of the rock and are now turning 13 years old are celebrating. Both the girl and the boy who are celebrating the Muchal ceremony are dressed in white clothes from head to toe on Navroz morning. It is intended that the future of these children will be bright and happy. A compact banquet table is spread on them, and this auspicious day is celebrated together with relatives, teachers, and friends of the child. On the morning of Navruz, both the girl and the boy who are celebrating the Muchal ceremony are dressed in white clothes from head to toe. With this, the future of these children will be bright and happy. A compact banquet table is spread on them, and this auspicious day is celebrated with relatives, teachers, and friends. According to the well-known folklorist Ohunjon Safarov from Bukhara, in the 1960s, in the middle of the house, where the table was spread with a large number of dishes, special zagoma-scales were hung from galvir-like dishes with leather bottoms, on which they put a child who was being tortured, and baldness stolen by this child. After that, they threw the child on the table, divided the baldness of his weight equally among the people around the table, and shared the meal. This is called a share. The custom of distribution of shares on behalf of those celebrating Muchal is still present in Bukhara.

Spring season in ancient Bukhara, social “Guli surh sayli” during Navruz period. It was formed on the basis of our people’s ancient totemistic views on flowers and has a long history. The red flower is unique in early spring when the tulips and tulips open. On this day, the residents of the city spread out from Nomozgoh square to Shirbudunu Bahauddin shrine. For this purpose, the names of the places of the village in the folk terms that are considered a separate language. Including:

Ark oldida gul sayli,
Gul sayliga kel mayli.

Bahouddin chorlaydi,

Erta sahar nahori

He said, among the famous historical monuments that have become a symbol of Bukhara, the name of Ark, Bahaiddin Naqshband shrine, is mentioned. During the festival, the popular dishes of Bukhara, especially” Halimpazlik, Halasapzlik” cooking, and kabob cooking, were on the rise. For this reason, the national termin for these dishes is presented in terms of the sayl:

Halisa- is a food of fair

Kochi- symbolized as a food of athletes

Halim- symbolized as a food of wise-man

During the flower procession, young men and women dressed in golden clothes, robes, and lovers tried to reveal their inner feelings to each other so there is a special reference in the terms of “Sayil” flower red: on the day of Sayil everyone is asked to forget old grudges and worries, to be in harmony with each other and celebrate with a good mood. In particular, the heads of orphans were patted on the day of the feast. Elderly, sick, lonely people were reported. Their consciousness is raised. The memory of the shooters is remembered. During the feasts of Sayil trumpets, trumpets and drums fill the surroundings. In the fields of Sayil, wrestlers fight, “Ko’pkari” on one side, cock or ram fighting on the other side, gatekeeper on the other side, curiosity and clowning, puppet shows are in full swing. And on the day of the fair, the stalls of artisans are fuller and more crowded than ever:

Rastalar buncha dolob,

Guldan tayyorlang sharob.

It is strongly condemned to drink alcohol, start a fight, spoil the mood of people. Sayil was led and controlled by the elders. Because of the popularity of “the Guli Surkh” holiday in Bukhara in the form of such a big celebration, mass parade, guests from other places also visited. Bukharans considered it a merit to participate in the Sayil flower parade. On this day, everyone tried to plant a sapling and contribute a little to this public event:

Har bahorda shu odat,

Xalq ogzida rivoyat,

Bittadan nihol ekish,

Guli surxga sadoqat.

Gul sayliga bormoq ham,

Bilib qoying bir savob.

So, the land of Bukhara has such unique ancient and traditional traditions. It is important for the younger generation to know about them. Navruz Udums, which embody the oldest spiritual traditions of our people, organize the public and call for new creative works, can have a spiritual and aesthetic effect on the education of a

mature generation, and first of all, they can fulfill the role of an important tool in educating young people with loyalty.

There are also darveshanas related to Navuz, which are celebrated differently in different regions. In particular, if you want to live in Bukhara, it is recommended. First of all, the issue of food is agreed upon. For “Darveshona food”, a cake is made of a kilogram of meat, charvi oil, and products of 7 types of grain crops: barley, corn, beans, peas, mash, wheat groats, and millet. Uzbek vegetables: carrots, turnips, and kadi (pumpkin) are used. Potatoes are not included. The table will be fixed with the power of the people. Someone bakes bread. Someone adds sugar. Halvoytar is prepared from it. It will be won. Somsa, ghoulki, and tuxum barak are cooked. Women, men, and children sit in a circle separately. Prayers are read. Can be taken away from food. Those who have consecutive condolence in their families are specially invited, but most of them try not to come. In Surkhandarya, it is organized and shot in places where martyrs are considered. For example, if a number of people were injured and died in the same place. For example, is it a river where people drown every year, is it a place where a lot of car accidents happen, etc.

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